

1 Single-cell transcriptomics reveal extracellular vesicles secretion with a cardiomyocyte 2 proteostasis signature during pathological remodeling

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28 Abstract

29 Aberrant Wnt activation have been reported in failing cardiomyocytes. Here we present single cell
30 transcriptome profiling of hearts with inducible cardiomyocytes-specific Wnt activation (β -cat ^{Δ ex3}) as well
31 as with compensatory and failing hypertrophic remodeling. We show that functional enrichment analysis
32 points to an involvement of extracellular vesicles (EVs) related processes in hearts of β -cat ^{Δ ex3}. A
33 proteomic analysis of *in vivo* cardiac derived EVs from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts has identified differentially
34 enriched proteins; including 20S proteasome constitutes, protein quality control (PQC), chaperones and
35 associated cardiac proteins; including α -Crystallin B (CRYAB) and sarcomeric components. The
36 hypertrophic model confirms that cardiomyocytes reacted with an acute early transcriptional
37 upregulation of exosome biogenesis processes and chaperones transcripts including CRYAB; which is
38 ameliorated in advanced remodeling. Finally, human induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSC)-derived
39 cardiomyocytes subjected to pharmacological Wnt activation recapitulated the increased expression of
40 exosomal markers, CRYAB accumulation and increased PQC signaling. These findings reveal that
41 secretion of EVs with a proteostasis signature contributes to early patho-physiological adaptation of
42 cardiomyocytes; which may serve as a read-out of disease progression and be used for monitoring
43 cellular remodeling *in vivo* with a possible diagnostic and prognostic role in the future.

44 Introduction

45 Stress conditions result in cardiomyocyte growth with increased oxygen demand accompanied by an
46 imbalanced vasculature growth ultimately resulting in deficient oxygen supply¹. This condition affects
47 cardiomyocytes' transcriptional profile activating adaptation processes. Due to an inefficient
48 regenerative capacity, cardiomyocytes react to myocardial insults with limited cellular adaptation,
49 ultimately resulting in substantial cellular loss². We have previously reported that mice with inducible
50 cardiomyocyte-specific β -catenin accumulation (β -cat ^{Δ ex3}) mimicked the molecular signature of
51 hypertrophic remodeling. β -catenin is the main transcriptional transducer of the Wnt signaling pathway
52 and was found increased in pathological heart remodeling in murine experimental models as well as in

53 human samples^{3,4}; indicating that β -catenin is an evolutionary conserved hallmark of cardiac stress. Wnt
54 signaling pathway has regenerative roles in development and disease⁵. However, activation of Wnt/ β -
55 catenin signaling specifically in cardiomyocytes resulted in molecular and phenotypic features of
56 pathological remodeling³. This was characterized by a cell-autonomous effect triggered by TCF7L2/ β -
57 catenin transcriptional activation in cardiomyocytes, resulting in cell-dedifferentiation with increased cell
58 cycle activity and heart failure^{3,6,7}. These data suggest a primary regenerative function of Wnt activation,
59 which is suppressed due to the lack of tissue plasticity in the adult heart.

60 Another example of Wnt regenerative function was described upon myocardial hypoxia, which induces
61 cardiomyocytes to release VEGF and potentially Wnt proteins that promote angiogenesis as a protective
62 effect. However, hypoxia can enhance Wnt signaling activity by stabilizing β -catenin and altering its
63 localization into the nucleus⁸; which in turn is deleterious for cardiomyocytes. Interestingly,
64 overexpression of β -catenin in skin fibroblasts converts them into therapeutically active cells that secrete
65 reparative EVs in the context of myocardial infarction and Duchenne muscular dystrophy⁹. This data
66 indicated distinct reparative and pathological roles of Wnt signaling activity in specific cell types. Today,
67 *in vivo* cell specific responses mediated by Wnt induction in cardiomyocytes are not completely
68 understood. In the present study, we aimed to further decipher these responses in a Wnt activation
69 model specifically in cardiomyocytes as well as in hearts upon hypertrophic stress. A powerful tool that
70 enabled us to decrypt individual cellular responses within tissues is single cell sequencing (SCS)¹⁰⁻¹³.
71 Using this methodology, we characterized the cardiomyocytes' stress response at single cell resolution,
72 advancing our knowledge in specific cellular responses contributing to organ remodeling. In order to
73 achieve translational significance of our findings, we combined a cardiomyocyte specific β -catenin gain-
74 of-function transgenic mouse model with experimentally induced hypertrophic remodeling in aged mice.
75 We identified an increased unconventional vesicular-mediated secretion of proteins associated with
76 mechanisms of stress. The vesicular-mediated secretion was validated in human induced pluripotent
77 stem cell (iPSC) models indicating an evolutionary conservation; what goes in line with previous
78 described roles of Wnt signaling in disease¹⁴.

79 Results

80 Single cell transcriptomics revealed enriched EV secretion in pathological β -cat ^{Δ ex3} 81 cardiomyocytes

82 Consistent with our previous observations³, we detected significantly enriched cardiac transcripts in
83 mouse hearts with β -catenin stabilization and Wnt target activation (β -cat ^{Δ ex3}) clustered to cell cycle,
84 transcriptional and developmental processes as well as Ubiquitin-like protein (Ubl), membrane-based
85 processes and secreted proteins (**Supplementary Figure 1A**). The latter gene ontology (GO) consisted
86 of genes involved in secreted vesicles (**Supplementary Figure 1B**). In order to investigate whether
87 secretion processes were activated by cardiomyocytes, we performed whole single cell transcriptome
88 analyses from ventricular tissue of β -cat ^{Δ ex3} and respective control hearts. By optimizing the isolation of
89 heart cells, we obtained enriched cardiomyocytes with typical rod-shaped morphology in control hearts.
90 Cardiomyocytes from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts showed the described abnormal morphology, namely bigger than
91 controls and with marked hypernucleation³ (**Supplementary Figure 2A and B**). After visualizing and
92 confirming that single cells were dispensed, they were subjected to sequencing with an emerging
93 described approach¹⁵⁻¹⁷ (**Supplementary Figure 2C and D**). To gain overall insights into the cellular
94 composition of these hearts, unsupervised clustering was applied. The entire cell population was
95 classified into major cell types, including cardiomyocytes (CMs), endothelial cells (ECs), fibroblasts
96 (FBs), pericytes (Per), neural like cells (NLC) and macrophages (M Φ) based on their respective
97 molecular markers^{13,18} (**Figure 1A and Supplementary Figure 2E**). Next, we subsetted these clusters
98 and performed pairwise differentially expressed genes (DEGs) analysis comparing control with β -cat ^{Δ ex3}
99 corresponding cell populations, focusing on cardiomyocyte and endothelial cell clusters (CM1, CM2 and
100 EC1 and EC2, respectively). We observed differences in the cell proportions towards an increase of
101 CM2 phenotype (**Supplementary Figure 2F**). CM1 and CM2 showed common and unique up-and-
102 down DEGs in β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts (**Supplementary Figure 2G**). A stress signature¹³ was identified in CM1
103 and CM2 clusters of β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts, in which CM2 showed more pronounced stress (**Figure 1B**).

104 Validating our protocol, DEGs that were previously identified by RNA-bulk sequencing analysis were
105 also identified in cardiomyocytes derived from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts³. They included stress, cell cycle markers
106 and Wnt targets (*Acta1*, *Ankrd1*, *Myh7*, *Ccnd2*, *Nppa*, *Dstn*, *Rock2*, *Bambi*) in CM1 and CM2 (**Figure**
107 **1C**). ECs showed significant increased cell cycle regulator *Ccnd2* and developmental regulators (*Anxa1*,
108 *Angpt1*, *Dhx32*, *Spry1*, *Adam10*) (**Figure 1D**). In line with our RNA bulk sequencing data and the failing
109 nature of the cardiomyocytes in β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts, we observed gene enrichment categorizing for
110 endosomal and vesicle-mediated transport including extracellular vesicles; multivesicular bodies
111 (MVBs), aggresome as well as protein quality control (PQC) processes, the hypoxia pathway (HIF-1 α
112 signaling), stress response and developmental processes for upregulated genes. Distinct processes in
113 CM1 included vascular smooth muscle contraction and proliferation, while CM2 showed process of
114 spliceosome, angiogenesis and fibroblast proliferation; indicating a paracrine function of these
115 cardiomyocytes. Common processes identified by enrichment analysis of downregulated genes for CM1
116 and CM2 categorized for lipid metabolism and heart development further in line with the failing condition
117 (**Supplementary Figure 3A and Figure 1E**). Overlapping enriched processes in EC1 and EC2 from β -
118 cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts included stress, PQC processes and secretion. EC2 showed unique processes
119 represented by angiogenesis, extracellular vesicles and cell cycle activity (**Figure 1F**). Macrophages,
120 pericytes and fibroblasts showed gene enrichment mainly clustering to stress pathways, secretion, PQC
121 and vesicular transport (**Supplementary Figure 3B**); all in line with the pathological cell remodeling and
122 consequent fibrosis displayed in the β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts³. These data suggested an activation of the Ub-
123 proteasome pathway, which was confirmed by higher levels of Ub-proteins in β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts (**Figure**
124 **1G**). These data distinguished specific biological activities of different cell populations in hearts with β -
125 catenin stabilization in cardiomyocytes, which characterized pathological cardiac remodeling.

126 **β -cat ^{Δ ex3} mice showed increased cardiac EV cargo secretion *in vivo***

127 To investigate the role of EV-mediated processes identified in the transcript enrichment, we investigated
128 the differential cardiac EV composition in this pathophysiological context. Transferability of EV secretion
129 studies *in vitro* to a disease-dependent condition is limited. Therefore, we decided to directly isolate EVs,
130 typically present in the interstitium of cellular tissues by using solid cardiac tissue of control and β -cat ^{Δ ex3}
131 mice based on adaption of previously described protocols¹⁹⁻²². As EV analysis *ex vivo* is challenging,
132 we reasoned that our genetic model holds an advantage by focusing on changes primarily initiated from
133 transcriptionally altered cardiomyocytes between control and β -cat ^{Δ ex3} in the extracellular compartment.
134 EVs were isolated from the concentrated heart homogenate by magnetic capture beads or differential
135 ultracentrifugation (UC) for biochemical characterization and proteomic analysis (**Supplementary**
136 **Figure 4A**). They were analyzed according to the minimal requirements for studies of EVs²³. Particle
137 size determined by nanoparticle-tracking-analysis (NTA) showed that the mean size of purified EVs was
138 160.0 \pm 69 nm. Furthermore, cholesterol containing vesicles were visualized using the hydrophilic
139 fluorescence analogue of cholesterol (Chol-PEG-KK114)²⁴ to label the P100 fraction (**Figure 2A**). This
140 fraction was further characterized by electron microscopic analysis, which showed small vesicles with
141 uniformly round and cup-shaped morphology with a 30- to 200-nm diameter²⁵ (**Figure 2B**). Further
142 validating the fraction obtained by UC, Western blot analysis demonstrated the presence of EV marker
143 CD81 in the P100 fraction, containing small EVs. In contrast, expression of Calnexin and GM130, which
144 generally represents ER and Golgi contamination, **respectively**²⁶, was absent (**Figure 2C**). Altogether,
145 these results demonstrated that we successfully isolated EVs from heart cell homogenates providing us
146 with, what we consider, an ideal platform for investigating *in vivo* produced EVs. Total protein contained
147 in the EVs was measured, which indicated no significant differences in the EV protein content between
148 control and β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts (**Supplementary Figure 4B**). The magnetic beads based-purified EV
149 fraction showed the pan exosomal marker TSG101 expression and the absence of the endoplasmatic
150 reticulum (ER) marker Calnexin, GAPDH and Vinculin, which were clearly present in cell pellets and in
151 the P16 fraction, containing major vesicles. By loading equal amounts of protein, we observed that
152 TGS101 expression was increased in β -cat ^{Δ ex3} isolated EVs (**Figure 2D**). We further aimed to gain
153 insight into the characteristics of EVs by analyzing the protein content and employed a label-free mass
154 spectrometry (MS) approach. From the MS data we detected and consistently quantified 573 proteins,
155 391 of which were significantly differentially enriched (213 increased) in preparations from β -cat ^{Δ ex3}

156 hearts (**Supplementary Figure 4C and Supplementary Data 1**). 45 of the proteins were included in
157 the Exocarta Top100 proteins found in EVs (**Supplementary Data 2**). Bioinformatic analysis revealed
158 that identified proteins clustered to processes previously described in EVs²⁶⁻²⁸ including extracellular
159 exosomes (270), acetylation (265), mitochondrial (182), metabolic pathway (110), Ubl conjugation (60),
160 Proteasome (25) and chaperone (19) (**Figure 2E**). Consistent with the endosomal origin of exosomes,
161 endosome-associated proteins were identified (**Supplementary Figure 4D**). The EVs characterized in
162 this study contained proteins found in classical small EVs or exosomes including CD81, ITGB1,
163 ATP1B1, EHD2, and TSG101; along with cell specific proteins including ENO1, PKM, CD47, ANXAX1
164 and cytoskeleton as well as sarcomeric proteins. This analysis confirmed an EV nature with a major
165 exosome representation and was therefore termed as *exosomes*. Applying the STRING functional
166 annotation protein interaction database to all identified proteins (573), we built a protein-protein
167 interaction (PPI) network, which clustered to carbon metabolism, exosomes, PQC processes as well as
168 cardiac proteins including cardiomyopathy (**Supplementary Figure 5A**). They were highly enriched in
169 proteins of the cardiovascular system (**Supplementary Figure 5B**). Using the same interaction
170 database, a PPI of the detected differentially enriched proteins (213) was performed. 202 nodes with
171 416 edges were identified and connected in this network with a statistical significance (p -value < 1.0E-
172 16). Several hubs were identified such as proteins involved in the exosome, PQC processes, PI3K/Akt
173 pathway, developmental and cardiomyopathy related proteins. Proteins enriched in exosomes from β -
174 cat ^{Δ ex3} were associated with heart tissue, further confirming the cardiac origin of the exosomes
175 (**Supplementary Figure 6A and B**). Thus, we deciphered an enriched EV fraction containing exosomes
176 with a cardiac proteome profile in line with the transcriptomic data.

177 **Cardiac exosomes from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} mice showed a distinct stress-related proteome signature**

178 Enrichment analysis of the proteins identified in the β -cat ^{Δ ex3} cardiac derived EVs included extracellular
179 exosomes, metabolic pathways, proteasome, Z disk, cell adhesion, and cardiomyopathies among others
180 (**Figure 3A**). Cluster analysis was performed on the predicted enriched 391 proteins in exosomes from
181 β -cat ^{Δ ex3} tissue using the K-means algorithm²⁹. The analysis resulted in a network with a high clustering
182 coefficient of 0.54 and with a PPI statistical significance (p -value < 1.0E-16). The vast number of
183 interactions indicated that the proteins are at least partially biologically connected. This analysis resulted
184 in three clusters (referred to as clusters 1, 2, and 3) with 87, 52 and 63-clustered proteins, respectively.
185 Enrichment analysis indicated that cluster 1 was enriched in metabolic proteins while cluster 2 and 3
186 were both enriched in PQC and exosomal processes. Additional cluster 3 proteins categorized to
187 cardiomyopathy and sarcomeric proteins exposed to constant mechanical stress, including Desmin
188 (DES), dystrophin muscular dystrophy (DMD); myosin binding protein C, cardiac (MYBPC3); myosin
189 light polypeptide 2 (MYL2); Titin (TTN) and phospholamban (PLN) (**Figure 3B, C and Supplementary**
190 **Figure 7A**). We further focused on cluster 3, featuring the greatest number of cardiac proteins. Using
191 the K-means algorithm, we detected two distinguished network sub-clusters (3A and 3B), with 42 and
192 22-clustered proteins, respectively and with a PPI statistical significance (p -value < 1.0E-16). Beside
193 extracellular exosome, GO analysis revealed that the cluster 3A contained mainly proteins involved in
194 cell adhesion, PI3K-Akt signaling pathway, laminin-complex, embryonic development and angiogenesis.
195 Sub-cluster 3B showed a protein network categorizing for Z disk proteins, HCM, DCM and hypoxia
196 response (**Figure 3D and E**). Thus, our proteomic data showed exosomal proteins as well as context-
197 heart-specific cargos. The sub-cluster networks of proteins may represent a pool of exosomes with
198 different cell signatures and specific biological roles in the context of cardiac remodeling.

199 β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts purified EVs were significantly enriched for all seven α and seven β chains of the 20S
200 proteasome components, while components of the 19S proteasome core were not enriched. We also
201 observed enrichment of molecular chaperones, co-chaperones and PQC associated proteins previously
202 described in secreted exosomes³⁰ such as HSPA70, HSP90AB1, VCP, UBE2N, PKACA and BAG2
203 (shown in Figure 3B). This went in line with the stress response of the β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts and elevated Ub-
204 proteins linked to pathologic remodeling. Next, we analyzed the levels of Ub-proteins in isolated EVs
205 and similar to the finding in the whole heart lysate, we observed increased levels of ubiquitinated
206 proteins in EVs from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts (**Figure 4A**). Furthermore, the small heat shock protein CRYAB,
207 that triages misfolded proteins for proteasomal degradation or repair in cardiomyopathy³¹, was enriched

208 in β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts purified exosomes. These proteins, associated to the Z disk, showed a close
209 interaction among the 20S core proteins, the chaperones and the cardiac proteins; suggesting a
210 common biological process (**Figure 4B**). We next incubated control and β -cat ^{Δ ex3} derived-exosomes
211 with mouse N2A neuroblastoma cells and immunolabelled for CRYAB. Confocal microscopy analysis
212 showed that, different to the perinuclear staining of CRYAB in both conditions (red arrows, **Figure 4C**),
213 increased accumulation of CRYAB in the membrane of cells treated with β -cat ^{Δ ex3} – cardiac derived
214 exosomes were observed (white arrows, **Figure 4C**). Next, exosomes were labelled with the membrane
215 dye CFSE. By Z-scanning, we observed that CRYAB co-localized with CFSE-labelled exosomes
216 attached to the cell surface (**Supplementary Figure 7B**). Furthermore, cells were stained for LAMP1
217 and Tubulin III, which are involved in vesicle trafficking and found co-localization of these markers with
218 the cell membrane, suggesting cellular attachment capacity (**Figure 4D**).

219 **Differential EV-transcriptional signature characterized early and late hypertrophic** 220 **cardiomyocyte populations**

221 We asked ourselves whether non-genetic modified cardiomyocytes upon pathological stress caused by
222 aging and cardiac hypertrophy are characterized by similar mechanisms. Therefore, we subjected aged
223 mice (1.5 years old) to pressure overload induced by transaortic constriction (TAC). Hypertrophy and
224 heart failure development was confirmed in the TAC group compared to the control sham group
225 (**Supplementary Figure 7C**). Hearts were prepared for SCS with a cardiomyocyte enriched fraction at
226 five days (early compensatory hypertrophy (CH)) and nine weeks (late failing hypertrophy (FH)) after
227 TAC. Unsupervised clustering revealed the presence of different cell types for all conditions
228 (**Supplementary Figure 7D**). We next focused on these cardiomyocytes and identified four distinct
229 cardiomyocytes sub-clusters (CM1-CM4) in each condition. The cluster CM2 was mainly found in cells
230 derived from TAC hearts at CH and FH. Only few cells of CM2 contributed to cardiomyocyte population
231 in sham CH. At a later stage, more cells contributed to this cluster in the control sham hearts; which may
232 be further associated to the aging process. Accordingly, CM2 showed an increased stress score (**Figure**
233 **5A**). A pairwise DEG analysis comparing TAC with sham of the corresponding cardiomyocytes clusters
234 revealed differential significant upregulation of hypertrophic stress and Wnt signaling markers in TAC
235 clusters (**Figure 5B**). This differential upregulation was higher at CH as compared to FH as shown by
236 the respective overall and individual scores (**Figure 5C and D**). At CH, GO analysis of upregulated
237 DEGs revealed that common processes with highly significant enrichment shared by all the clusters
238 included EVs, cell adhesion, PQC processes, hypertrophy and development as well as hypoxia signaling
239 pathways. At FH, highest commonly enriched processes included cytoskeletal proteins and remodeling,
240 natriuretic peptide, cell hypertrophy and stress, blood vessel remodeling as well as alpha crystallin/Heat
241 shock protein (**Figure 5E**). Extracellular vesicular processes were enriched at FH mainly in CM2 in line
242 with the more stress signature of this cluster (**Supplementary Figure 8A**). Exosomal markers (*Cd9*,
243 *Cd81*, *Cd63*) and *Cryab* were significantly upregulated in all CM clusters at an early stage of remodeling
244 with a reduced differential expression at late remodeling (**Figure 6A and B**). The exosome and hypoxic
245 score were significantly higher in TAC cardiomyocytes at CH and FH stages (**Figure 6C and D**).
246 Overlapped enriched processes between common DEGs from TAC and the β -cat ^{Δ ex3} cardiomyocytes at
247 CH, categorized to extracellular exosome, proteasome and proteolysis processes. At FH common DEGs
248 categorized to development, cytoskeleton remodeling and hypertrophy; indicating a hallmark of stress
249 in these cells (**Supplementary Figure 8B**). Altogether, these results indicated that EV, hypoxia and
250 PQC signaling are concomitantly and acutely activated in cardiomyocytes upon cardiac remodeling.

251 **Human iPSC-derived cardiomyocytes upon stress stimulus activate EV-stress signaling**

252 In order to investigate if the identified mechanism can be reproduced in human cells, we derived
253 cardiomyocytes from human iPSCs and triggered stress by activating Wnt signaling to mimic our *in vivo*
254 β -cat ^{Δ ex3} model. We treated the iPSC-derived cardiomyocytes with GSK-3 β inhibitor (CHIR-99021),
255 which led to accumulation of β -catenin and activation of the Wnt signaling pathway³² or DMSO as control
256 for five days and medium was collected for isolation of EVs (**Supplementary Figure 9A**). As a control
257 for inducing cardiomyocyte stress, we also treated the cells with TGF- β ³³. We confirmed increased
258 nuclear translocation of the transcriptionally active (phosphorylated (P) Ser675) β -catenin (**Figure 7A**),

259 as well as significantly increased number of cells expressing KI67 in CHIR-treated iPSC-derived
260 cardiomyocytes (**Supplementary Figure 9B**); in line with the role of Wnt activation in cell cycle
261 activity^{3,32}. By equal protein loading of EVs isolated from CHIR-treated iPSC-derived cardiomyocytes,
262 we observed increased levels of TSG101; which was similar to the EVs isolated from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts in
263 the isolated exosomal fraction and to a lesser extent in TGF- β treated cells. The absence of calnexin
264 was confirmed in the exosomal fraction isolated from supernatant of iPSC-derived cardiomyocyte
265 cultures (**Figure 7B and Supplementary Figure 9C**). Similar to the *in vivo* finding, we observed
266 increased levels of ubiquitinated proteins in EVs from CHIR-treated iPSC-cardiomyocytes (**Figure 7C**).
267 Next, we performed a rescue experiment in which Wnt transcriptional activation was blocked by adding
268 Isoquercetin, which interferes with the binding of β -catenin and the TCF/LEF transcription factors³⁴. EVs
269 isolated from these treated iPSC-cardiomyocytes showed increased expression of TSG101 upon CHIR-
270 treatment with a partial rescue upon Isoquercetin treatment. This goes in line with the increased
271 transcriptionally active (non-phosphorylated) Ser33/37/Thr41) β -catenin in whole cell lysates of CHIR-
272 treated iPSC-cardiomyocytes, with a non-significant reduction upon concomitant Isoquercetin treatment
273 (**Figure 7D and E**). Next, treated cells were stained with CRYAB and cardiac Troponin 2 (TNNT2)
274 antibody and subjected to confocal microscopy analysis. This showed clear perinuclear accumulation of
275 CRYAB in TNNT2-positive cells, which was increased as demonstrated by semiquantification of the
276 stained area, in the CHIR-treated iPSC-derived cardiomyocytes (**Figure 7F and Extended Figure 9D**),
277 although total CRYAB protein levels were unchanged as shown in **Supplementary Figure 9C**. This
278 data corroborated that Wnt activation is sufficient to induce stress in human cardiomyocyte-like cells
279 and is able to increase EV-mediated transport of stress markers of the Ub-proteasomal pathway and
280 the CRYAB chaperone, all corresponding to our *in vivo* data.

281 Discussion

282 Active Wnt/ β -catenin signaling was proved to be associated with hypertrophic heart remodeling in
283 mouse models and human biopsies in multiple cell types including cardiomyocytes^{3,4,14,35-38}. Accordingly,
284 activation of β -catenin in cardiomyocytes resulted in molecular and phenotypic features of hypertrophic
285 remodeling³. Moreover, cardiomyocyte-specific deletion of β -catenin showed an attenuated TAC-
286 induced hypertrophic remodeling^{3,39}, indicating a beneficial effect of lowering Wnt activity in disease. We
287 previously showed that β -catenin stabilization and concomitant transcriptional activation in
288 cardiomyocytes resulted in increased transcription of developmental and cell cycle regulators. This
289 enhanced transcriptional activation leads to cardiomyocytes polynucleation, suggesting endo-
290 reduplication rather than newly formed myocytes, and is subsequently followed by heart failure³,
291 indicating that persistent reactivation of the cell cycle is not beneficial in adult cardiomyocyte. This is
292 similar to the mechanism driving by the Hippo signaling pathway, which induces proliferation⁴⁰ as well
293 as cardiomyocyte dedifferentiation and dysfunction upon long-term activation in postnatal
294 cardiomyocytes. Thus, it seems that the activation of the Wnt cascade stimulates adaptation,
295 dedifferentiation and proliferation of mammalian myocytes; however, the response may be determined
296 by environmental and mechanical cues as well as the developmental plasticity of the cardiomyocytes.
297 Our present study showed that EV-mediated secretion was stimulated in Wnt activated and stressed
298 cardiomyocyte, which might be part of a compensatory adaptive response.

299 In line with the knowledge that EVs secretion is increased upon hypoxia^{28,30,41}, we observed enrichment
300 of hypoxic signaling in those cardiomyocytes. This goes in line with both, the role of Wnt/ β -catenin
301 signaling enhancing hypoxia via HIF-1 α pathway and via the hypoxia response, due to increased oxygen
302 consumption in cardiac hypertrophy^{1,42}. Further secretion functions identified in β -catenin gain-of-
303 function cardiomyocyte clusters included angiogenesis and smooth muscle contraction. This was
304 accompanied by endothelial cells with an active angiogenic profile and supports previous studies
305 showing a vascular program induced by cardiomyocytes with Wnt activation in the adult heart⁴³. Other
306 studies showed that HIF1 α in cardiomyocytes was inversely correlated with capillarization⁷, indicating
307 that cardiomyocytes are central for the phenotypic change of surrounding cells. We observed that stress
308 scores were significantly increased in TAC cardiomyocytes at CH while these scores were less
309 significant at FH, indicating a transcriptional adaptation in advanced remodeling. Another common
310 feature of the different cardiomyocyte clusters in the heart of β -cat ^{Δ ex3} mice and early stage of induced
311 hypertrophy was the activation of EV-related processes. Increased expression of exosomal markers

312 was attenuated in late remodeling, strongly indicating that EV secretion processes are part of an
313 adaptive response. Most available data on cardiac exosomes, mainly produced in cell culture
314 experiments, indicated that their release can be enhanced by hypoxia and stress conditions^{28,30,41} in line
315 with our finding. Moreover, induced exosome production during hypoxia has cytoprotective effects in
316 renal tubular cell injury⁴⁴. Altogether, this provides evidence that activation of the Wnt signaling along
317 with the hypoxic response and EV-mediated secretion are part of the cardiomyocytes' transcriptional
318 adaptive signatures upon stress.

319 EVs, including exosomes (or cardiosomes), were described to be released from all major heart cell types
320 *in vitro*, however it is unclear to what extent this relates to the situation *in vivo*⁴⁵. In this study, we
321 analyzed EVs in a pathophysiological *in vivo* context. Although no EV isolation method yet exists that
322 can be considered as a gold standard, especially for tissue, differential UC has long been regarded as
323 a reliable technique and was employed in this study in combination with magnetic bead-based
324 separation^{46,47}. We have obtained highly consistent preparations of 30- to 200-nm diameter EVs, which
325 expressed a set of previously described EV markers characterizing exosomes as well as showed the
326 absence of common impurities^{48,49}. In line with established guidelines^{23,47}, we characterized their size
327 and morphology as well as fluorescently labelled purified EVs demonstrating colocalization with recipient
328 cell proteins *in vitro*. MS analysis confirmed that the highest enriched processes, to which all proteins
329 confidently categorized were previously described in EVs^{26,27}. They include tetraspanins, integrins,
330 growth factor receptors, cytoskeletal proteins, ESCRT-related proteins, chaperones, metabolic proteins,
331 mitochondrial proteins and proteins involved in vesicle trafficking (annexins, major histocompatibility
332 complex (MHC) class I and class II), as well as sarcomeric proteins^{30,50}. Several of these proteins were
333 shown increased upon hypoxia⁴¹ and were enriched in the proteome of EV derived from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts
334 in our analysis. More importantly cardiac proteins DES, DMD, MYBPC3, MYL2, TTN, VPC, CD47 and
335 PLN were enriched; strongly supporting the cardiac origin of these vesicles. Our findings therefore
336 provide evidences for increased loading of exosomes with chaperones and sarcomeric proteins in the
337 stressed cardiomyocytes of Wnt activated hearts *in vivo*.

338
339 Significantly enriched proteins in the EV isolated from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts categorized to Ub-proteasomal,
340 metabolic and vesicular-mediated pathways along with hypertrophic cardiomyopathy. Further sub-
341 clustering of the cardiac protein networks revealed a group of proteins categorizing to cell adhesion,
342 PI3K-Akt signaling pathway and angiogenesis processes and another sub-cluster classifying to Z disk
343 proteins, HCM, DCM and hypoxia response. This suggests different origins of EVs with an endothelial
344 and a cardiomyocyte-like signature, respectively. Specifically, β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts purified exosomes were
345 significantly enriched for protein quality control processes including the 20S proteasome, Ub pathways,
346 chaperones and co-chaperones previously described in secreted exosomes such as HSPA70,
347 HSP90AB1, CRYAB, PKACA and BAG2^{28,51}. Of note, PKACA was identified as partners and regulator
348 of murine cardiac 20S proteasomes⁵² as well as CRYAB, a Z-line protein and the most abundant small
349 HSP constitutively expressed in cardiomyocytes. CRYAB interacts with cardiac proteins including DES
350 and TTN to prevent stress-induced aggregation or to trap prone damaged proteins upon stress^{53,54}.
351 Accordingly, we have identified loading of sarcomeric proteins prone to aggregation including DES and
352 TTN in cardiac exosomes from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} failing hearts. This is in line with the nature of Z-disk proteins
353 that are targeted by the PQC system due to constant mechanical strain, leading to stress-induced
354 misfolding. A mouse expressing a missense (R120G) dominant CRYAB mutant in cardiomyocytes,
355 showed intrasarcoplasmic amyloidosis and resulted in cardiac hypertrophy⁵⁵. This was accompanied
356 with an impaired proteolytic function of the Ub-proteasome system⁵⁶. Upon acute brain ischemia-
357 reperfusion, cardiac CRYABR120G mice showed increased inflammation with large CRYAB protein
358 aggregates positive for ubiquitin staining in the brain. Similarly to our finding in this study showing
359 accumulation of CRAYB in N2A cells treated with exosomes derived from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts, exosomes
360 isolated from the blood of CRYAB(R120G) mouse model induced pronounced CRYAB protein
361 aggregation in primary neuronal cultures⁵³. It was previously demonstrated that CRYAB is able to
362 interact with the proteasome 20S Subunit Alpha 3 (PSMA3), playing important roles in the degradation
363 of bound substrates or facilitating the degradation by the proteasome⁵⁷. Large aggregates may remain
364 inaccessible and impair the Ub-proteasome system activity upregulating lysosomal-autophagy-like

365 processes^{58,59}. This process may be activated in stressed cardiomyocytes, allowing CRYAB and
366 interacting components sequestration into nascent lysosomal vesicles, which are redirected to be
367 released as exosomes^{60,61}. In our study, we identified PSMA3 amongst the cargos in the exosomes
368 derived from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts as well as proteins involved in Ub signaling. Our data further suggests the
369 role of an exosome-loaded with a proteostasis associated machinery at the interface of the proteasomal
370 and endosomal-lysosomal network upon stress conditions in cardiomyocytes. This hypothesis is based
371 on the fact that exosome biogenesis is highly interconnected with the lysosomal degradation pathway.
372 The endosomal pathway generates intraluminal vesicles (ILVs) that subsequently form MVBs and a
373 hybrid organelle termed amphisome, which can either fuse to the autophagic pathway via
374 autophagosomes or be released as exosomes by fusion with the plasma membrane⁶². Ubiquitinated
375 proteins can serve as markers, which are recognized and imported into a subset of ILVs that are
376 eventually secreted as exosomes⁶³. Accordingly, we have observed increased ubiquitinated proteins in
377 EVs from Wnt activated stressed cardiomyocytes. Thus, stress conditions may favour a vesicular,
378 unconventional secretory pathway of damaged proteins and associated machinery, possibly upon
379 lysosomal system overload⁶⁴⁻⁶⁸ (Figure 8). Similarly, an increase of exosomal cargoes abundance was
380 observed in mutated CRYAB(R120G) exosomes compared to wild-type derived exosomes along with
381 associated misfolded proteins. This may be required for the targeting of misfolded proteins to the
382 exosome^{69,70}. In line with this, significant upregulated genes categorizing to vesicle-mediated transport,
383 late endosome, phagosome and MVB processes as well as protein folding, chaperones, proteasome
384 and Ubl-pathways were observed in stressed cardiomyocytes. This may represent the interconnection
385 of cellular PQC mechanisms, whereby misfolded proteins can either be refolded, degraded, or delivered
386 to extracellular compartments⁷¹. Our data showed increased exosomal loading of protein along with their
387 ubiquitination upon stress caused by Wnt activation in mouse and in human iPSC-derived
388 cardiomyocytes, indicating a common EV response. Enhanced, loaded EVs were also observed in
389 iPSC-derived cardiomyocytes upon hypertrophic TGF- β stimulus to a lesser extent indicating a primary
390 role of stress in this process. Rescuing Wnt activation resulted in a mild reduction of the increased
391 exosome cargoes, indicating that Wnt activation, but more specifically stress, is responsible for the
392 described phenotype.

393
394 In summary, this study characterized the proteomic cargos of cardiac derived EVs in an *in vivo* context
395 of failing cardiomyocytes. Here, we complemented the analysis of Wnt activated cardiomyocyte *in vivo*,
396 in order to precisely study the mechanisms driven by Wnt signaling, with a hypertrophic stress model,
397 as a translational approach. Furthermore, we extended our analysis on human derived cardiomyocytes
398 to study the evolutionary conservation of the identified mechanism. It revealed an increased EV
399 mediated process associated with proteins of the Ub-proteasome system released by cardiomyocytes,
400 suggesting their contribution to hypertrophic disease adaptation. It is tempting to speculate that the
401 increased cellular stress induces protein misfolding, leading to an excess of ubiquitination and activation
402 of chaperone-mediated processes, which are redirected as exosomal release. This may represent an
403 additional “back-up” system, by which cells alleviate the accumulation of intracellular aggregate-prone
404 or misfolded proteins. As such, this could ultimately limit the pathogenesis and the onset of misfolding
405 associated disease mechanisms, and in perspective, represent a potential target to develop novel
406 therapeutic intervention⁷². It may be interesting to identify the presence of these EVs in the circulating
407 blood as previously demonstrated in cardiomyocyte-derived EVs, which were present in the circulation
408 and reflecting cardiac injury that can serve as biomarker of cardiac injury^{73,74}. The EV protein cargo
409 composition associated with proteostasis functions of the cardiomyocytes make them attractive potential
410 biomarkers to detect cardiac health⁷⁵. Finally, since exosomes are messengers from one cell to another,
411 secretion of unwanted material to the extracellular environment may have an impact, beneficial or
412 detrimental, on neighbouring cells⁶³ and therefore deserves further investigation.

413 414 **Material and Methods**

415 **Animals**

416 Both male and female mice were included in the study and were kept in a 12 h day/night cycle with *ad*
417 *libitum* feeding. The generation of the heart-specific β -catenin gain-of-function (β -Cat ^{Δ ex3}) mouse model
418 was previously described³ (C57BL/6N background). Briefly, for transgene induction in β -Cat ^{Δ ex3}, heart-
419 specific expression of the Cre recombinase under control of the *Myh6* promoter was activated by
420 administration of Tamoxifen (T5648, 30 mg/kg body weight/day; Sigma–Aldrich) intraperitoneal for 3
421 days. Wild-type β -catenin and Cre recombinase positive littermates were used as control for β -Cat ^{Δ ex3}
422 mice. Genotyping was performed as previously described³ with the following primers: Fwd: 5'
423 GCTGCTGTGACACCGCTGCGTGGAC 3' Rev: 5' CACGTGTGGCAAGTTCGCGTCATCC 3' using
424 the REExtract-N-Amp PCR ReadyMix (Sigma-Aldrich). Transverse aortic constriction (TAC) was
425 performed in 17,5 months-old (average) mice as previously described^{3,7}. The intervention was
426 performed by tying a braided 5-0 polyviolene suture (Hugo Sachs Elektronik) ligature around the
427 transversal aorta and a blunted 26-gauge needle and subsequent removal of the needle. For sham
428 controls the suture was not tied. To determine the level of pressure overload by aortic ligation, a high
429 frequency Doppler probe was used to measure the ratio between blood flow velocities in right and left
430 carotid arteries. TAC mice with blood flow gradient <60% were excluded. Echocardiography analysis
431 were done at different time points and for that, mice were anesthetized with 2% isoflurane inhalation
432 and ventricular measurements were performed with a VisualSonics Vevo 2100 Imaging System
433 equipped with a MS400, 30 MHz MicroScan transducer. The observer was unaware of the genotypes
434 and treatments. All procedures were performed by the SFB 1002 service unit (S01 Disease Models). All
435 animal experiments were approved by the animal research review board Lower Saxonian State Office
436 for Consumer Protection and Food Safety (Niedersächsisches Landesamt für Verbraucherschutz und
437 Lebensmittelsicherheit (LAVES)) (AZ-G 20.3434).

438 **Single cell sample preparation**

439 Bulk RNAseq was previously published³. For SCS, a modified Langendorff perfusion was performed.
440 Mice were anesthetized with isoflurane. Hearts were dissected and canulated via the ascending aorta
441 with a 18G blunt-end needle and retrogradely perfused with Perfusion Buffer (150 mmol/L NaCl, 5
442 mmol/L HEPES, 5.4 mmol/L KCl, 10 mmol/L glucose, 2 mmol/L Na-pyruvate, 1.2 mmol/L MgCl₂ · 6 H₂O,
443 10 mmol/L taurine, 12.38 mmol/L 2,3-butanedione monoxime, pH 7.35). Hearts were enzymatically
444 digested with Digestion Buffer (210 μ g/mL Liberase DH (Roche), 25 μ mol/L CaCl₂ in Perfusion Buffer)
445 for 10 min at 37 °C, minced into tissue pieces, homogenized by pipetting with a 10 ml serological pipette
446 to yield a single cell suspension of rod-shaped cells. Debris was removed by washing with Exchange
447 Buffer (0.5 w/v % bovine serum albumin, 200 μ mol/L CaCl₂ in Perfusion Buffer) and gravitational settling
448 of tissue pieces for 1 min.

449 **Single cell library preparation**

450 Samples were prepared, processed and analyzed for single cell transcriptomics at NIG, Institute of
451 Human Genetics, University Medical Center Göttingen. Briefly, cells were distributed on 5,184 nanowell
452 chips ICELL8 250v Chip (ICELL8 System, Takara Bio). Single alive cells were identified using Hoechst
453 33342 and propidium iodide staining (NucBlue Cell Stain Reagent, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and the
454 CellSelect Software (Takara Bio). Complementary DNA synthesis was performed by oligo-dT priming in
455 a one-step RT-PCR reaction. P5 indexing primers, Terra Polymerase and Reaction Buffer were added
456 for library preparation. Transposase enzyme and reaction buffer (Tn5 mixture) were added to each well.
457 P7 indexing primers were dispensed to wells. Final libraries were amplified and pooled as they are
458 extracted from the chip. Pooled libraries were purified and size selected with Agencourt AMPureXP
459 magnetic beads (Beckman Coulter) to obtain an average library size of 500 bp. Libraries were
460 sequenced with a HiSeq4000 (Illumina) to obtain on average $\sim 3 \cdot 10^5$ reads per cell (single-end, 50 bp).

461 **SCS Data analysis**

462 Raw sequencing files (bcl-files) were converted into a single fastq file using Illumina bcl2fastq software
463 (v2.20.0.422) for each platform. Each fastq file was demultiplexed and analysed using the Cogent NGS
464 analysis pipeline (CogentAP) from Takara Bio (v1.0). In brief, cogent demux wrapper function was used
465 to allocate the reads to the cells based on the cell barcodes provided in the well-list files. Subsequently,

466 cogent analyze wrapper function performed read trimming with cutadapt⁷⁶(version 3.2), genome
467 alignment to *Mus musculus* genome GRCm38 using STAR⁷⁷ (version 2.7.7a), read counting for exonic,
468 genomic and mitochondrial regions using featureCounts⁷⁸ (version 2.0.1) and utilizing *Mus musculus*
469 gene annotation version 102 from ENSEMBL and generating a gene matrix with number of reads
470 expressed for each cell in each gene. Raw gene matrices underwent quality control (QC) filtering for
471 cells and genes using the following parameters: (a) for cells, only those with at least 2500 genes and
472 less than 30 % of mitochondrial reads, and (b) for genes, only those containing at least 100 reads
473 mapped to them from at least 3 different cells. The bioinformatic analysis was performed using the
474 Seurat package (version 4.1.2)⁷⁹. Expression matrices were split by Chip and, after normalization by
475 'NormalizeData' using default settings and selection of the 2000 most variable features using
476 'FidVariableFeatures'. Integration of the datasets was performed by the standard parameters of
477 'IntegrateData'. Data was scaled and centered by 'ScaleData', regressing out the variability caused by
478 the mitochondrial percentage and the Depth of the sequencing. Dimensions were reduced using
479 'RunPCA'. Afterwards, 'FindNeighbors' (dimension parameter = 1:9) and 'FindClusters' (granularity
480 parameter = 0.3) were run and the clusters were visualized, after UMAP reduction was calculated by
481 using Louvian algorithm. Gene ontology (GO) analyses were performed using default parameters and
482 stringency in 'ClueGO' (Cytoscape)⁸⁰ and DAVIS. The significant gene ontologies (GO) are shown with
483 $p < 0.05$. The cardiomyocyte stress, hypoxia and EV scores were calculated by the expression of
484 established markers per cell¹³. Ggplot²⁸¹, Dplyr⁸² and EnhancedVolcano packages were used for data
485 visualization⁸³.

486 **Exosome Isolation**

487 For proteomic analysis and cell treatment, cardiac EV isolation from mouse hearts was performed with
488 Langendorff perfusion as described above. The hearts were disconnected from the Langendorff
489 apparatus, atria were separated and ventricles were minced in a petri dish with 2.5 mL Exchange buffer.
490 The homogenate was transferred to a Falcon tube and the Petri dish was rinsed with an additional 5 mL
491 of Exchange buffer, which was also transferred to the Falcon tube. Non-digested heart tissue was
492 allowed to sediment for 1 min. Supernatant was filtered through a 40 μm cell strainer. All steps took
493 place at 4 °C. Exosomes were isolated using subsequent steps of centrifugation. First, samples were
494 centrifuged at 2,000 x g for 10 min to pellet remaining cells, cell debris and large apoptotic bodies. In
495 the next step supernatants were centrifuged at 14,000 x g for 35 min to remove microvesicles and other
496 large extracellular vesicles. Supernatants were transferred to ultracentrifugation tubes and centrifuged
497 at 100,000 x g for 2 h at 4 °C. Pellets were then washed with PBS and recentrifuged at 100,000 x g for
498 1,5 h. Supernatants were kept (S100) and pellets resuspended (P100) in 50-100 μl of PBS or RIPA
499 buffer for Western blot and stored at -20 °C until further analysis. For biochemical characterization,
500 cardiac EV isolation from mouse hearts and supernatants obtained from human iPSC-derived
501 cardiomyocytes was performed by positive selection Magnetic Activated Cell Sorting (MACS). The mice
502 hearts were removed and placed in a 35 mm PBS Petri dish. Then, the hearts were sliced using a sterile
503 scalpel and dissociated until having a homogenous size of approximately 2x2x2 mm. After that, the
504 pieces were transferred into a 6 well plate and immediately enzymatically digested using Liberase (1
505 mg/mL) for 30 min at 37 °C. Subsequently, the lysate was transferred to a fresh 15 mL tube and
506 homogenized using a 1 mL pipette. Tissue was allowed to settle for a minute and next the supernatant
507 was removed and filtered using a 40 μm cell strainer into a 50 mL tube. Following this, removal of cellular
508 debris by serial centrifugation (2,000 x g and 10,000 x g) digested ventricles or supernatants were
509 incubated for 1 h with Isolation kit MicroBeads (Mouse Exosome Isolation kit Pan, Miltenyi Biotec). After
510 incubation, labeled EV were loaded on a magnetic column, washed to remove unlabeled vesicles and
511 eluted with PBS for protein quantification and for Western blot analysis.

512 **Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM)**

513 TEM grids (copper, 150 hexagonal mesh, Science Services, Munich, Germany) which were coated with
514 a formvar film were put on top of 10 μl droplets of the exosome fraction and incubated for 10 min. Then,
515 the grids were washed 5 times with PBS followed by incubations on droplets of water. For contrasting,
516 the grids were stained for 5 min on droplets of uranylacetate-oxalate, followed by 5 min incubation on

517 droplets of a 1:9 dilution of 4% uranylacetate in 2% methylcellulose. These solutions were prepared as
518 described⁸⁴. After blotting the methylcellulose from the grids using filter paper and drying of the
519 methylcellulose film, samples were imaged with a LEO912 transmission electron microscope (Carl Zeiss
520 Microscopy, Oberkochen, Germany) and images were taken using an on-axis 2k CCD camera (TRS,
521 Moorenweis, Germany).

522 **Nanoparticle Tracking Analysis (NTA)**

523 The size distribution of the serum exosomes was analyzed using a Malvern Panalytical NS300
524 instrument equipped with nanoparticle particle tracking software (Version NTA 2.3 Analytical Software).
525 According to the manufacturer's recommendation, the samples were illuminated by the laser (Blue 488)
526 and the movement of nanoparticles due to Brownian motion was recorded for 60 s at a mean frame rate
527 of 20 frames per second. Each process was repeated three times. sEV particles were diluted in PBS
528 (1:100). Camera level 14, screen gain 10.8, detection threshold 5. For each sample, a total of three
529 videos of 30-60 s was measured. The videos were analyzed by the NanoSight NTA and the particles'
530 concentration, size distribution and the general mean and mode of the samples were obtained.

531 **Western Blot Analysis (WB)**

532 Proteins were extracted from EV preparation and tissue by addition of lysis buffer (150 mmol/L sodium
533 chloride, 1.0% NP-40 or Triton X-100, 0.5% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS (sodium dodecyl sulfate),
534 50 mmol/L Tris) or 10 mmol/L Tris/HCl pH 7.5; 150 mol/L NaCl; 0.5 mmol/L EDTA; 0.5% NP-40)
535 containing proteases and phosphatases inhibitor cocktail (Roche). After clarification (12,000 xg at 4 °C,
536 20 min), protein concentration was quantified with Bradford assay and the different samples were
537 resuspended in sample buffer. Bio-Rad system was used to run the blots, at constant 120 V, followed
538 by semi-dry transfer at constant 140 mA. After blocking (3% BSA in TBST) the membranes were
539 incubated with primary antibodies overnight (**Supplementary Data 3**). Membranes were incubated in
540 secondary antibody for 1-2 h at room temperature (anti-mouse IgG (H+L) HRP conjugate (Bio-Rad)
541 1:1,000), developed (ECL Amersham) and imaged using ChemiDoc Touch Imaging System (Bio-Rad).
542 All unedited blots are provided in Supplementary Figure 10.

543 **Liquid Chromatography Coupled to Tandem Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS/MS)**

544 Samples were reconstituted in 1x NuPAGE LDS Sample Buffer (Invitrogen) and applied to 4-12%
545 NuPAGE Novex Bis-Tris Minigels (Invitrogen). Samples were run 1 cardiomyocyte into the gel for
546 purification and stained with Coomassie Blue for visualization purposes. After washing, gel slices were
547 reduced with dithiothreitol (DTT), alkylated with 2-iodoacetamide and digested with trypsin overnight.
548 The resulting peptide mixtures were then extracted, dried in a SpeedVac, reconstituted in 2%
549 acetonitrile/0.1% formic acid/ (v:v) and prepared for nanoLC-MS/MS⁸⁵. All samples were spiked with a
550 synthetic peptide standard used for retention time alignment (iRT Standard, Schlieren, Schweiz). Protein
551 digests were analyzed on a nanoflow chromatography system (Eksigent nanoLC425) hyphenated to a
552 hybrid triple quadrupole-TOF mass spectrometer (TripleTOF 5600+) equipped with a Nanospray III ion
553 source (Ionspray Voltage 2400 V, Interface Heater Temperature 150 °C, Sheath Gas Setting 12) and
554 controlled by Analyst TF 1.7.1 software build 1163 (all AB Sciex, Darmstadt, Germany). In brief, peptides
555 were dissolved in loading buffer (2% acetonitrile, 0.1% formic acid in water) to a concentration of 0.3
556 µg/µl. For each analysis 1.5 µg of digested protein were enriched on a precolumn (0.18 mm ID x 20 mm,
557 Symmetry C18, 5 µm, Waters, Milford/MA, U.S.A) and separated on an analytical RP-C18 column (0.075
558 mm ID x 250 mm, HSS T3, 1.8 µm, Waters) using a 90 min linear gradient of 5-35% acetonitrile/0.1%
559 formic acid (v:v) at 300 nl min⁻¹. Qualitative LC/MS/MS analysis was performed using a Top25 data-
560 dependent acquisition (DDA) method with an MS survey scan of *m/z* 350–1250 accumulated for 350 ms
561 at a resolution of 30,000 full width at half maximum (FWHM). MS/MS scans of *m/z* 180–1,600 were
562 accumulated for 100 ms at a resolution of 17,500 FWHM and a precursor isolation width of 0.7 FWHM,
563 resulting in a total cycle time of 2.9 s. Precursors above a threshold MS intensity of 125 cps with charge
564 states 2⁺, 3⁺, and 4⁺ were selected for MS/MS, the dynamic exclusion time was set to 30 s. MS/MS
565 activation was achieved by CID using nitrogen as a collision gas and the manufacturer's default rolling
566 collision energy settings. Two technical replicates per sample were analyzed to construct a spectral

567 library. For quantitative analysis, MS/MS data were acquired using data-independent acquisition (DIA)
568 with 65 variable size windows⁸⁶ across the 400-1,050 *m/z* range. Fragments were produced using rolling
569 collision energy settings for charge state 2⁺, and fragments acquired over an *m/z* range of 350–1400 for
570 40 ms per segment. Including a 100 ms survey scan, this resulted in an overall cycle time of 2.75 s. 3
571 technical replicates were acquired for each sample. Protein identification was achieved using
572 ProteinPilot Software version 5.0 build 4769 (AB Sciex) at “thorough” settings. The combined qualitative
573 analyses were searched against the UniProtKB mouse reference proteome (revision 12-2017, 60717
574 entries) augmented with a set of 52 known common laboratory contaminants to identify proteins at a
575 False Discovery Rate (FDR) of 1%. Spectral library generation and SWATH peak extraction were
576 achieved in PeakView Software version 2.1 build 11041 (AB Sciex) using the SWATH quantitation
577 microApp version 2.0 build 2003. Following retention time correction using the iRT standard, peak areas
578 were extracted using information from the MS/MS library at an FDR of 1%⁸⁷. The resulting peak areas
579 were then summed to peptide and finally protein area values per injection, which were used for further
580 statistical analysis in Perseus 1.5.6.0 software (Max Planck Institute for Biochemistry, Martinsried,
581 Germany). STRING (Search Tool for the Retrieval of Interacting Genes/Proteins) (<http://string-db.org/>)
582 was used for network analysis. Gene ontology (GO) analyses were performed using default parameters
583 and stringency in ‘ClueGO’ (Cytoscape)⁸⁰ and DAVIS.

584 **Exosome labelling**

585 For immunofluorescence analysis, the exosome pellet was resuspended in PBS and stained with Chol-
586 PEG-KK114 (kindly provided by Volker Westphal and Stefan Hell, Max-Planck-Institute for Biophysical
587 Chemistry^{24,88}). Exosomes isolated from one heart were incubated with Chol-PEG-KK114, diluted 1:100
588 from a 100 µmol/L stock solution, for 30 min at RT, washed with PBS twice by ultracentrifugation, fixed
589 and placed on coverslips for imaging in Zeiss LSM 710 NLO confocal microscope. For EV protein
590 labelling, 250 µL diluted EV samples (containing 2 µg Exosomes) were incubated with 5 µM
591 Carboxyfluorescein succinimidyl ester (CFSE) (Thermo Fischer Scientific) in microtiter wells for 45 min
592 at 37 °C. Cells were incubated with labelled exosome dilutions in a Yokogawa high-content screening
593 system and observed for 3 h (37 °C, 7% CO₂). The pinhole was set to 50 µm.

594 **Human induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC)-derived cardiomyocytes**

595 Human iPSC LiPSC-GR1.1 (TC1133 or RUCDRi002-A)⁸⁹ were cultured on Growth Factor Reduced
596 Matrigel (BD Biosciences) in StemMACS iPSC-Brew XF, human (Milteny Biotec) differentiated by WNT
597 modulation into iPSC-derived cardiomyocytes (Base Medium: RPMI 1640 + GlutaMAX, 2% B27
598 supplement (Thermo Fisher Scientific), 200 µmol/L L-ascorbic acid, 1 mmol/L Na-pyruvate, 100 U/mL
599 penicillin, 100 µg/mL streptomycin (Gibco)) by mesoderm induction with 9 ng/mL Activin A (Bio-Techne),
600 1 µmol/L CHIR99021 (Merck Chemicals GmbH), 5 ng/ml BMP4 (Bio-Techne) and 5 ng/mL FGF
601 (PeproTech) for three days followed by cardiac differentiation by WNT inhibition with 5 µmol/L IWP4
602 (ReproCELL Europe Ltd.) for 9 days. Cardiomyocytes were metabolically selected (RPMI 1640 without
603 glucose, 2.2 mmol/L Na-lactate, 100 µmol/L β-mercaptoethanol (Gibco), 100 U/mL penicillin, 100 µg/mL
604 streptomycin) for a total period of approximately four weeks before treatment. iPSC-derived
605 cardiomyocytes were treated with 10 µmol/L CHIR99021 (Merck Chemicals GmbH) alone or in
606 combination with 150 µmol/L Isoquercetin (Selleck Chemicals GmbH), 10 pmol/L TGFB1 (Peprotech)
607 or DMSO as control prepared in RPMI1640 without glucose, 4 mmol/L Na-pyruvate, 200 µmol/L L-
608 ascorbic acid, 2% B27 supplement minus insulin, 100 U/mL penicillin, 100 µg/mL streptomycin for five
609 days in a 12-well plate. Supernatant was collected every day and pooled for EV isolation. Cells that were
610 cultured on Matrigel (Corning) coated coverslips were fixed and used for immunofluorescence analysis.

611 **Immunohistochemistry**

612 For immunofluorescence, Neuro2A cells (ATCC CCL-131) and iPSC-derived cardiomyocytes plated on
613 Matrigel (Corning) coated glass coverslips were fixed with 4% PFA, followed by PBS washing and
614 permeabilization with 0.2% BSA and 0.3% Triton X-100 in PBS for 10 min. Cells were then blocked with
615 5% BSA and 0.1% Triton X-100 at RT. Primary and secondary antibodies (**Supplementary Data 3**)
616 were diluted in 2% BSA and 0.1% Triton in PBS. Coverslips were mounted with ProLong Gold medium

617 containing DAPI (Invitrogen). Murine heart tissues were dissected, rinsed in PBS, fixed in 4% PFA over
618 night at 4 °C, embedded in paraffin and sectioned at 3 µm thickness using a Leica microtome. Paraffin
619 embedded sections were de-paraffinized, rehydrated and antigen was unmasked by microwaving
620 sections for 10 min in 10 mmol/L sodium citrate buffer, pH 6. Sections were blocked at RT for 1 h with
621 5% BSA and 0.1% Triton X-100 in PBS. For immunostaining, primary antibodies (**Supplementary Data**
622 **3**) were incubated over night at 4 °C. Next, sections were washed in PBS and incubated with the
623 corresponding secondary IgG-Alexa488, 594 or 633 antibodies (1:200, Molecular Probes). Slides were
624 imaged using a Zeiss LSM 710 NLO confocal microscope. Fluorescence intensity was analyzed with
625 ZEN lite 2012 software.

626 **Data availability**

627 The mass spectrometry proteomic dataset generated during the current study is available in the
628 ProteomeXchange Consortium via the PRIDE⁹⁰ partner repository with the dataset identifier
629 PXD031113, the bulk RNAseq data is available at NCBI GEO under accession GSE97763, the raw and
630 normalized Single Cell RNAseq data is available at <https://owncloud.gwdg.de/index.php/s/NeSJGuf2o2yc2qn>. Reporting of the EV protocol is available at EV-TRAC⁹¹
631 including the MISEV2018²³ (ID: EV220418). The uncropped Western blots in Supplementary Figure 10.
632

633 **Code availability**

634 The full code used during the current study is available at https://github.com/fblec/Stressed_CMs_EVs.

635 **Statistics and Reproducibility**

636 G-Power3.1 was used to determine the sample size for animal studies. For single cell analysis, *a priori*:
637 compute required sample size, was used. Sample size per group=105 (Effect size d=0.5, power=0.95,
638 comparison of two independent groups). For mice interventions, sample size per group=3 (Effect size
639 d=0.9, power=0.85, comparison two independent groups). Statistical analyses were performed using
640 GraphPad PRISM 7. Two-tailed unpaired student's t-tests were conducted on two group comparisons.
641 Pearson's correlation was performed for correlation plots. Statistical significance was assumed when p
642 < 0.05 (*). Specific statistics applied for proteomic and transcriptomic analysis are mentioned in the
643 corresponding sections.

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653 **Author Contributions**

654 E.S, F.B., G.G. and L.C.Z. are responsible for overall design of this study. E.S, F.B. G.G., C.R., P.T.,
655 I.S. and L.C.Z carried out experiments, data analysis, and interpretation. C. L. analyzed proteomic data.
656 W. M. performed EM. M. Sitte and G. S. performed SC sequencing and primary QC. Z. V., Z. G. and J.
657 C. G. contribute to EV isolation protocol establishment. F. B. performed bioinformatic analysis. L. C. Z.
658 wrote the paper. E.S, F.B. and G.G. contributed to the preparation and revision of the paper. M. Samak.,
659 R. H. and J. C. G. revised the paper. All authors have given approval to the final version of the paper.

660 **Competing interests**

661 The authors declare no competing interests.

662

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902 **Figure 1: Dysregulated genes and processes in cardiomyocytes and endothelial cells from β -**
903 **cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts. a.** Representative uniform manifold approximation and projection (UMAP) plot after
904 scRNA-seq and data integration of cardiac cells isolated from control (673 cells) or β -cat ^{Δ ex3} (601 cells)
905 hearts. Six cell clusters were identified and exclusively classified to cardiomyocytes (CM), endothelial
906 cells (EC), fibroblast (FB), pericytes (PC), macrophage (MC) and neural like cells (NLC) in both
907 conditions. **b.** UMAP plot of cardiomyocyte subclusters CM1, CM2) with respective hypertrophic stress
908 score as defined by the expression of *Acta1*, *Nppa*, *Nppb* and *Ankrd1*. **c.** Dot plot depicting expression
909 of selected cardiac stress and Wnt signaling target transcripts in cardiomyocytes from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} and
910 control hearts as indicated. **d.** Selected top categories from GO biological processes enrichment of
911 upregulated DEGs in CM1 and CM2 of β -cat ^{Δ ex3} representing transcriptional responses. **e.** Dot plot
912 depicting expression of selected developmental and angiogenesis transcripts in endothelial cells (EC1
913 and EC2) from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} and control hearts as indicated. **f.** Selected top categories from GO biological
914 processes enrichment of upregulated DEGs in EC1 and EC2 of β -cat ^{Δ ex3} representing transcriptional
915 responses in endothelial clusters. GO enrichment represents $-\log_{10}$ p-value (p-value <0.05) and term
916 fusion was applied. **g.** Increased Ub-protein abundance in β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts versus control. Staining free
917 gel is provided as loading control.

918 **Figure 2: Increased cardiac EV cargo secretion in β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts. a.** Nanoparticle tracking analyses
919 (NTA) confirmed isolation of extracellular vesicles with a mean size of 160.0 \pm 69 nm. Visualization of
920 the purified vesicles by hydrophilic fluorescence analogue of cholesterol (Chol-PEG-KK114) staining. **b.**
921 Electron microscopy confirmed the isolation of round and cup-shaped particles, typical for exosomal
922 vesicles less than 200 nm in size. **c.** Western blot showing expression of the exosome marker CD81 in
923 the higher speed-centrifugation fraction (P100) from mouse hearts and the absence of Golgi-marker
924 GM130 and endoplasmic reticulum marker Calnexin, which were present in the cell pellets and lower-
925 speed centrifugation (S100). **d.** Western blot showing increased exosomal marker TSG101 in EV
926 isolated from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts versus control, as well as showing absence of Calnexin, GAPDH and
927 Vinculin expression in both conditions upon equally amount of loaded proteins as visualized by the stain
928 free gel image. **e.** GO biological processes distribution of enrichment analysis of total proteomic data
929 (573 proteins) obtained from isolated vesicles of β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts and control confirming an association
930 of vesicle contained proteins with “extracellular exosomes” (n=2 (each a pool of 2-3 hearts) biological
931 replicates and technical triplicates for NTA and MS analysis, n=4, biological replicates for Western blots)
932 GO enrichment represents $-\log_{10}$ p-value (p-value <0.05) and term fusion was applied.

933 **Figure 3: Stress-related proteome signature in cardiac exosomes from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts. a.** GO
934 biological processes distribution of enrichment analysis of significant enriched proteins identified in
935 isolated vesicles from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts versus control. **b.** Heatmap of cluster analysis using STRING
936 functional annotation protein interaction database on the predicted enriched loading proteins in
937 exosomes from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} tissue using the K-means algorithm.^{29 29 29 28 28 28 27} **c.** Three ontological clusters
938 were identified: Cluster 1 (metabolism); Cluster 2 (proteasome associated proteins) and Cluster 3
939 (cardiomyopathy associated proteins). **c.** GO biological processes analysis of the different clusters. **d.**
940 Further subclassification of the Cluster 3 in sub-clusters 3A and 3B and **(e)** associated GO biological
941 processes. GO enrichment represents $-\log_{10}$ p-value (p-value <0.05) and term fusion was applied.

942 **Figure 4: Ub-proteasomal-related proteome signature in exosomes from β -cat ^{Δ ex3}**
943 **cardiomyocytes. a.** Increased Ub-protein abundance in β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts versus control. Staining free
944 gel is provided as loading control. **b.** Protein-protein interaction analysis using STRING functional
945 annotation database on the predicted enriched proteasome, chaperones and cardiac proteins identified
946 in β -cat ^{Δ ex3} exosomes including CRYAB. **c.** Representative confocal images of immunofluorescence
947 staining of Neuro2a cells that were exposed to β -cat ^{Δ ex3} and control derived-cardiac exosomes and
948 stained for CRYAB. Perinuclear staining (red arrows) and increased protein accumulation (white arrows)
949 was observed in recipient cells (n=3, technical replicates). **d.** Representative confocal images of
950 immunofluorescence staining of Neuro2a cells that were exposed to carboxyfluorescein succinimidyl
951 ester (CFSE)-*ex vivo* labelled exosomes from β -cat ^{Δ ex3} hearts, stained with Tubulin III (TUBIII) and
952 LAMP1 (n=3, technical replicates). The white box (i) indicates the region that is depicted at the right side

953 showing the different staining (ia-id). Hoechst33342 was used for nucleus visualization. Scale bar = 20
954 μm .

955 **Figure 5: Differential EV-signaling in cardiomyocyte populations upon hypertrophic remodeling.**
956 **a.** UMAP plot of unbiased reclustering of the cardiomyocyte cluster identified after scRNA-seq and data
957 integration. Cells were isolated from control (sham) and hypertrophic (transaortic constriction (TAC))
958 hearts at an early compensatory (CH) and late failing (FH) stages (average of 650 cells per condition
959 and stage). Four sub-clusters were identified (CM1-CM4). Corresponding hypertrophic stress score as
960 defined by the expression of *Acta1*, *Nppa*, *Nppb* and *Ankrd1* is depicted for all cells. **b.** Representative
961 dot plots showing expression levels for the stress genes *Myh7*, *Nppa*, cardiac Wnt-target genes *Dstn*,
962 *Rock2*, *Bambi*, *Ccnd2* and Wnt inhibitors *Kremmen1*, *Shisa4*, *Apc* in clusters CM1-CM4 from sham and
963 TAC hearts of CH (left) and FH (right) stages. **c-d.** Violin plots showing Wnt signaling target and stress
964 scores in the different CM clusters for CH (c) and FH (d) stages. **e.** Selected top categories from GO
965 biological processes enrichment of overlapping DEGs obtained from sham vs TAC comparison in CH
966 (left) and FH (right). GO enrichment represents $-\log_{10}$ p-value (p-value <0.05) and term fusion was
967 applied.

968 **Figure 6: Increased exosomal and hypoxic scores in cardiomyocyte populations upon**
969 **hypertrophic remodeling. a-b.** Representative violin plots showing expression levels for the cardiac
970 chaperone *Cryab* and exosomal makers *Cd9*, *Cd81* and *Cd63* in clusters CM1-CM4 from sham (pink)
971 and TAC (orange) hearts of CH (a) and FH (b). **c-d.** Hypoxia (c) and exosomal scores (d) in sham and
972 TAC cardiomyocytes in CH and FH.

973 **Figure 7: Increased exosomal cargo release in human iPSC-derived cardiomyocytes upon Wnt**
974 **activation. a.** Confocal immunofluorescence images showing nuclear translocation and accumulation
975 of the transcriptionally active P-Ser675-CTNNB1 in TNNT2-positive iPSC-derived cardiomyocytes upon
976 CHIR99021 (CHIR) treatment validating WNT/ β -catenin signalling induction *versus* DMSO control
977 treated cells. **b-c.** Western blot showing increased (b) TSG101 levels and (c) Ubiquitinated protein
978 abundance in exosomal preparations from CHIR treated iPSC-derived cardiomyocytes *versus* control
979 (DMSO), (TGF β 1 was included as additional stress control in b) upon equal amounts of loaded proteins
980 as visualized by the stain free gel image (biological replicates n=3 (b) and n=2 (c) technical replicates).
981 In (b) exosome preparation from β -cat Δ ex3 and control hearts were included for direct comparison. **d.**
982 Western blot and corresponding quantification showing increased TSG101 levels in exosomal
983 preparations from CHIR treated iPSC-derived cardiomyocytes *versus* control (DMSO) and a partial
984 rescue upon concomitant treatment with Iso-Quercetin (Iso QC), blocking Wnt transcriptional activity. **e.**
985 Western blot showing transcriptionally active CTNNB1 and CRYAB expression in cell lysates from CHIR,
986 Iso QC and CHIR/Iso QC treated iPSC-derived cardiomyocytes. **f.** Confocal immunofluorescence
987 images showing cytosolic accumulation of CRYAB in CHIR-treated iPSC-derived cardiomyocytes.
988 Hoechst33342 was used for nucleus visualization and corresponding semiquantification are depicted,
989 which is showing the intensity of CRYAB staining normalized to the total TNNT2 intensity (n=6, technical
990 replicates, biological duplicates). Scale bar = 20 μm . Data are shown as mean \pm SEM; unpaired
991 student's t-test.

992 **Figure 8: Scheme summarizing the finding in this study.** Our study revealed an increased EV-cargo
993 secretion including Z-disk proteins prone to misfolding (DES, TNN), proteasome components and
994 chaperone associated proteins by cardiomyocytes upon Wnt activation and pressure overload induced
995 stress. This was accompanied by a concomitant activation of hypoxia response, which is known to
996 activate EV-mediated processes. This response was more accentuated in early compensatory
997 hypertrophic remodeling, suggesting their contribution to hypertrophic disease adaptation, and may
998 overlap with the endosomal autophagic pathway at the formation of amphisomes, also activated upon
999 stress. It is tempting to speculate that increased cellular stress induces protein misfolding, which triggers
1000 an excess of ubiquitination and CRYAB-mediated processes activation and the amphisomes are
1001 redirected to the exosomal release. Created with BioRender.com.

e GO: Biological processes CM1

f GO: Biological processes EC1

GO: Biological processes CM2

GO: Biological processes EC2

e

GO:Biological processes distribution

- 21.36% extracellular exosome (270)
- 20.97% Acetylation (265)
- 14.40% mitochondrion (182)
- 9.41% poly(A) RNA binding (119)
- 8.70% Metabolic pathways (110)
- 5.54% focal adhesion (70)
- 4.75% Ubl conjugation (60)
- 4.59% Methylation (58)
- 2.37% cadherin binding involved in cell-cell adhesion (30)
- 1.98% proteasome complex (25)
- 1.58% Dilated cardiomyopathy (20)
- 1.50% Hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (19)
- 1.50% Chaperone (19)
- 1.34% proteolysis in cellular protein catabolic process (17)

a

Compensatory hypertrophy (CH) stage

b

Failing hypertrophy (FH) stage

c

Hypoxia score in CH stage

Hypoxia score in FH stage

d

Stress-exosome score in CH stage Stress-exosome score in FH stage

a

b

c

d

e

f

Wnt activation
Hypertrophy

